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RE: OPEN SOURCE SCIENCE (OSS) FOR NASA EARTH SYSTEM OBSERVATORY
(ESO) MISSION SCIENCE DATA PROCESSING STUDY REQUEST FOR
INFORMATION

RESPONSES TO QUESTIONS 1, 2, 3, & 4

To the Open Source Science Study Team Steering Committee ,

Thank you for the opportunity to respond to the request as part of the Open Source Science (OSS) for NASA Earth System Observatory (ESO) Mission Science Data Processing Study.¹

Our comments here reflect our collective perspective as scientists, open source software developers, open science advocates, and founding members of the Pangeo Project.² For context, the Pangeo Project is a community effort with the goal of enabling Big Data geoscientific research and addressing systemic problems in the computational sciences such as reproducibility. Since its inception in 2016, Pangeo has evolved into a nexus of collaboration for the open source scientific Python ecosystem, working to better integrate available software tools for research and developing new approaches for cloud-base scientific computing.³ The name Pangeo has also come to describe three distinct but related components: the open source community engaged with the project, an integrated ecosystem of scientific Python software projects, and a cloud-based platform for scientific computing. Our comments below reflect our experiences across all of these components and we have made specific efforts to distinguish between them where appropriate.

Topic Area 1: Data Processing System Architecture

At the core of Pangeo's architectural design is the understanding that monolithic end-to-end platforms are not capable of meeting the diverse needs and data types of modern geoscientific

¹ NASA, [Open Source Science for the Earth System Observatory Mission Science Data Processing Study](#) (Jan. 6, 2022).

² Pangeo, [A community platform for Big Data geoscience](#) (Jan. 31, 2022).

³ Gentemann et al., [Science Storms the Cloud](#) (May 5, 2021).

research.^{4,5,6} As a result, the Pangeo community has focused efforts on developing an interconnected but modular ecosystem of tools and infrastructure capable of being deployed in multiple configurations and tailored to specific applications, including science data processing systems.

At its core, the Pangeo platform is made up of six primary components: 1) a user interface (e.g. Jupyter Notebooks), 2) a data model (e.g. Xarray), 3) a parallel task scheduler (e.g. Dask), 4) a system for managing computing resources (e.g. Kubernetes), 5) a data storage system (e.g. AWS S3), and 6) and analysis ready data stores and catalogs (e.g. Zarr and Intake). While the examples listed above are commonly used together in Pangeo's cloud deployments, the modular architecture supports swapping individual components. For example, to deploy the same concept in an High-Performance Computing environment, replace Kubernetes with a batch scheduler (e.g. PBS) and AWS S3 with a parallel file system (e.g. Lustre).

Separable from the Pangeo Platform itself but no less integral to its success is the need to co-locate compute and data. As data volumes trend toward the petabyte scale, it becomes increasingly difficult to compute on data stored remotely. Pangeo has focused significant effort on the development of Analysis-Ready, Cloud-Optimized (ARCO) data stores,^{7,8} data formats (e.g. Zarr), and catalog interfaces to collections of data (e.g. STAC and Intake). The concept of data-proximate computing is of course highly relevant to operational data processing, as it minimizes latency and maximizes throughput within the system. Pangeo's "cloud-native" I/O approaches would thus have major performance advantages for an operational data processing system.

Pangeo has mainly been focused on exploratory analysis and batch processing of large datasets (i.e. 10s-100s TB) by individual scientists and analysts. However, the same set of core technologies can easily be adopted to streaming and real-time processing using event-driven architecture (e.g. replacing the interactive Jupyter interface with pub-sub-style or schedule-based triggers).⁹ Moreover, there are deep advantages to having operational data processing environments closely mirror those used by everyday scientists: much quicker prototyping and operationalization of new algorithms; and greater transparency of the processing chain. Some new development would be required to fully realize this potential, specifically

⁴ Pangeo, [Technical Architecture](#) (Feb. 1, 2022).

⁵ Robinson et al., [Seven Principles for Effective Scientific Big-Data Systems](#) (June, 2020).

⁶ Abernathey et al., [Closed Platforms vs. Open Architectures for Cloud-Native Earth Systems Analytics](#) (Mar. 30, 2020).

⁷ Abernathey et al., [Cloud-Native Repositories for Big Scientific Data](#) (June 15, 2021).

⁸ Stern et al., [Pangeo Forge: Crowdsourcing Analysis-Ready, Cloud Optimized Data Production](#) (In Press).

⁹ We note that the Pangeo-Forge project, discussed under Topic Area 3, is using a batch-style environment for processing ARCO datasets.

around deploying Xarray and related tools in a serverless framework and deploying notebooks in an operational context.¹⁰ Note that notebooks are not required within Pangeo, but they have the advantage of being fully self-documenting computational artifacts, which could prove advantageous in an operational context.

Topic Area 2: Open Science

We strongly support NASA's adoption of open science practices. In the paragraphs below, we outline specific recommendations in the areas of open source software, analysis ready data, and version control and software sharing.

Open source software underpins huge swaths of the global research apparatus and is critically under supported.^{11,12} As many open science activities and NASA science missions depend on open source software, we encourage NASA to continue finding opportunities to provide funding to active projects.¹³ Beyond encouraging NASA to fund open source software, we also suggest NASA find opportunities to incentivize staff participation in open source software development.¹⁴

Open source software can play two distinct roles in the context of operational data processing. First, the data processing system itself can be assembled from existing open source components (e.g. NumPy, Xarray), leading to faster development and easier maintenance.¹⁵ Where integration of components is required, we encourage NASA to work with "upstream" software communities and find common solutions to general problems. Having as few bespoke components to the data processing system as possible is the most sustainable path. Second, the data processing chains themselves can be open source and published on a platform like GitHub. By providing total transparency into the processing of every product, NASA would greatly enhance trust while also engaging the community in the development of new algorithms and maintenance of widely used tools. There would also be a strong educational benefit; instructors in geosciences and data science could use these real-world processing pipelines as examples, case studies, and homework assignments.

¹⁰ Ufford et al., [Beyond Interactive: Notebook Innovation at Netflix](#) (Aug. 16, 2018).

¹¹ National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, [Open Source Software Policy Options for NASA Earth and Space Sciences](#) (2018).

¹² Muna et al., [The Astropy Problem](#) (Oct. 11, 2016).

¹³ NASA, [Support for Open Source Tools, Frameworks, and Libraries](#) (Aug. 23, 2021).

¹⁴ For example, Google provides time and resources for employees that contribute to open source projects; See Google, [Open Source](#) (Feb. 1, 2022).

¹⁵ See Topic Area 3 for additional comments on applications of open source software in this context.

We cannot overemphasize the importance of analysis-ready, cloud-optimized data in the context of future data processing systems.¹⁶ Beyond providing a critical building block on which scalable processing systems can be built, ARCO data is also a key part of open and reproducible science. When combined with clear data provenance, analysis ready data allows processing systems to skip many of the most laborious and error-prone parts of operational pipelines.

Topic Area 3: Component Technologies

Embracing mature open source software libraries as the dependencies of future NASA ESO will improve the accessibility and sustainability of future data system architectures. We provide summaries of key libraries in the Pangeo ecosystem below with example use cases for each:

- [Xarray](#) is a Python project for working with multidimensional labeled arrays and datasets. It provides an extensive toolkit on top of its NetCDF-like data model and interoperates with many parts of the scientific Python ecosystem (e.g. Numpy, Dask, Matplotlib, Pandas, etc.). In operational data processing systems, Xarray has the potential to act as a core data model, standardizing component interfaces and facilitating interoperability.
- [Dask](#) is a library for parallel computing in Python. It is integrated directly within Xarray but also supports more generic DAG-based parallel computing. Dask's wide range of deployment options (including [HPC](#) and [Kubernetes](#)) support portability and help avoid vendor lock-in.
- [Filesystem-spec](#) (*fsspec*) provides a common filesystem-like interface to multiple storage interfaces (local, S3, FTP, etc.) in Python. As an interface and compatibility layer, *fsspec* provides transformative functionality enabling efficient remote access to data.
- [Kerchunk](#) is a Python library that provides a unified way to represent a variety of chunked, compressed data formats (e.g. NetCDF/HDF5, GRIB2, TIFF), allowing efficient access to the data from traditional file systems or cloud object storage. This addresses one of the key challenges facing NASA during its move to the cloud where there is tension between serving data archival formats (e.g. HDF) or cloud-optimized data formats (e.g. Zarr).¹⁷
- [Xpublish](#) provides a web server interface on top of Xarray datasets, providing an approach for serving derived datasets on demand.¹⁸ This approach is especially valuable in cases where the volume of derived data products makes their storage cost prohibitive relative to the cost of recomputation. Additionally, the ability to turn any Xarray dataset into a web service supports third-party sharing of derived data products.

¹⁶ Abernathey et al., [Cloud-Native Repositories for Big Scientific Data](#) (June 15, 2021).

¹⁷ Signell et al., [Cloud-Performant NetCDF4/HDF5 Reading with the Zarr Library](#) (Feb. 26, 2020)

¹⁸ Hamman, [Publishing Xarray Datasets via a Zarr-compatible REST API](#) (Ma. 9, 2020).

- [Pangeo-Forge](#) is an open source tool for data extraction, transformation, and loading of scientific data into analysis-ready, cloud-optimized (ARCO) formats.¹⁹ The project is developing tooling and infrastructure to support programmatic ARCO data creation. Future science data processing systems could take advantage of the Pangeo-Forge's open source tooling for converting mission data to ARCO formats.

Topic Area 4: Downstream Interoperability.

Although the previous sections focused on Pangeo's applicability in the context of mission science data processing systems, many of the core elements of the Pangeo Project are also applicable to downstream data use. Here we focus on specific areas where improvements in end-user interfaces will benefit scientific researchers.

- ARCO data: at present, much of NASA's existing mission data is stored in archival formats (e.g. NetCDF) and distributed via HTTP or FTP endpoints. To enable more efficient and performant access, NASA should provide mission data in analysis-ready cloud-optimized data formats and distribute the data via cloud storage. NASA should also strive to limit barriers to use of ARCO data held in cloud storage, such as providing a variety of Cloud-native authentication mechanisms.
- Advanced data catalogs: The processes of data discovery and data access are key challenges for end users of NASA data. Adoption of community-embraced standards for data cataloging and metadata dissemination, such as the Spatio Temporal Asset Catalog ([STAC](#)), must be part of future data data processing systems. Supporting programmatic search, discovery, and data access (e.g. [Intake](#)), advanced data cataloging tools, combined with ARCO data formats, will allow end users to seamlessly work with mission data. The NASA CMR STAC prototype²⁰ provides key pieces of functionality toward this goal and we encourage NASA to continue developing this approach.
- Support the development of mission focused open source software: An important companion to the data system foundations described in this comment is well-supported domain-focused software tooling. This tooling should be co-developed by researchers and mission data system engineers such that it meets the needs of downstream users while taking full advantage of data system capabilities. One such example is the [icepyx](#) project, which provides Python tools for obtaining and working with ICESat-2 data hosted by NSIDC DAAC²¹. Continued support of domain-focused open source tooling is encouraged.

¹⁹ Stern et al., [Pangeo Forge: Crowdsourcing Analysis-Ready, Cloud Optimized Data Production](#) (In Press).

²⁰ NASA, [CMR STAC GitHub Repository](#) (Feb. 1, 2022).

²¹ Scheick et al., [icepyx: Python tools for obtaining and working with ICESat-2 data](#) (2019).

Thank you for the opportunity to submit comments. We would be glad to meet with NASA or JPL staff if we can be helpful as you continue to develop the Open Source Science initiative.

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